

Anticancer mechanisms of action: Alantolactone

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Abstract:

In modern societies, cancer is regarded as a one of the toughest challenges to overcome internally, and it has, time and again, placed a significant socioeconomic burden on human societies. Over the years, it has been demonstrated that a variety of medications containing natural ingredients can treat a wide range of conditions, such as infections, cancer, atherosclerosis, neurological disorders, and inflammatory issues. Sesquiterpene lactones (STLs) are a class of natural chemicals with a variety of biological uses.

Among them, a type of STL which is Alantolactone (ALT) is of particular note because of the focused attention it has received recently. By studying cancer cells for some time now, a plethora of studies have been carried out on the molecular mechanics of how this compound interacts with cancer cells, and its results are suggesting that the primary mechanism of this compound lay in the ability to induce free radicals and block active complex signaling pathways that contribute to the aggravation of the cancer cell mass. This paper aims to review the most recently introduced ALT molecular mechanisms proposed by different researchers. Alantolactone is a naturally occurring compound present in the traditional Chinese medicinal herb *Inula helenium* L. It shows promise in the treatment of various diseases. Recent studies conducted in laboratories and on animals have indicated that alantolactone can exhibit toxicity against several cancer types, including liver, colorectal, and breast cancers. The efficacy of alantolactone is affected by specific cancer-related pathways and anomalies within cancer cells.

Keywords: Sesquiterpenelactone, Alantolactone, Anticancer, Apoptosis, Metastasis, Cell cycle

Introduction :

According to recent research, Non Communicable Diseases (NCDs) are the top killers across the world. The NCD that plagues the world most and economically burdens the society heavily is cancer. With regards to cancer and its related fatalities, studies have shown a correlation in its prevalence along with population growth, aging, and changing lifestyles[1-3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has alarming forecasts regarding cancer predicting it will increase at a staggering rate of over 70% in the next two decades. WHO also lists the top six cancers with the highest occurrence rate. In women, the types of cancer commonly observed are breast, lung and bronchial, colorectal, and uterine cancers. In men, the prevalent forms include prostate, lung and bronchial, colorectal, urinary bladder, and melanoma cancers. Enhancing awareness of the fundamental causes and risk factors associated with cancer can play a significant role in its prevention.[4-

[5]. From gathered information in recent decades, cancer has been classified as a multi-causative disorder. This means that the progression of cancer is caused by the interrelationship of both genetic and environmental components. The onset of carcinogenic changes can be produced by several entities from outside the body in addition to genetic mutations [6-7]. Various elements, including nutrition, medications, alcohol consumption, smoking, infectious agents, chemical exposure, and lifestyle choices, significantly contribute to the development of cancer. It is also imperative that the coupling of genetic elements with the environmental factors is paid special attention to [8]. Over the past few decades, genetic technology, bioinformatics, and proteomics have made significant progress in unraveling the complex system of cancer. Even with continuous research, there have been few notable breakthroughs in the treatment or cure of cancer, suggesting that much more needs to be done in this area. This has led to significant efforts to find novel treatment drugs that are both highly effective and lowly harmful in the fight against cancer [9]. Many years have gone by, yet natural substances that are used as readily available medical resources to treat malignant tumors have attracted the interest of countless scientists. At the same time, a number of ancient natural substances derived from plants have shown remarkable effectiveness in treating a variety of illnesses, most notably cancer [10]. Natural compounds including phenolic acids, flavonoids, and sesquiterpenes have been demonstrated in numerous studies to have anti-tumor capabilities and a wide range of impacts on cancer and other illnesses. Sesquiterpene lactones (STLs) are a particular class of natural substances that fall under the sesquiterpenoids category [11]. The plant kingdom contains a large number of these compounds, particularly in the Asteraceae family, where over 5,000 distinct STLs have been identified. According to research on several sesquiterpene lactones, these substances may have strong anti-cancer effects on a variety of cancer types. Some, such as thapsigargin, artemisinin, and parthenolide, are underrepresented in cancer clinical trials, nevertheless. Researchers have recently become interested in ALT, a sesquiterpene lactone, because of its many biological actions, which include anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and anti-cancer benefits. According to recent research, ALT can help treat cancer by causing apoptosis, preventing metastasis, and inhibiting cell growth and proliferation in a variety of cancer cell types. Research on ALT and the most recent understanding of its mechanisms of cancer inhibition are compiled in this review [12,15].

➤ **The natural products role in cancer treatment :**

The term "natural products" refers to a broad range of substances that come from bacteria, fungus, plants, and marine life. These substances have the potential to be used in the creation of novel drugs since they are more complex, bioactive, and structurally diverse than synthesized pharmaceuticals. Natural products are among the best treatments for a variety of malignancies, according to research [16]. By targeting several cancer-related processes, such as growth, metastasis, apoptosis, differentiation, and angiogenesis, these substances may be able to inhibit the growth and progression of tumors, according to mounting data. Natural chemicals are an essential source for the discovery of novel drugs in the intricate process of drug development. Scientists can find and create novel medications to treat a variety of illnesses, especially cancer, by comprehending the molecular mechanics of these organic substances [17,18].

Many studies show that around half of all drugs come from natural sources, and about 80% of chemotherapy drugs are also derived from these natural products. These substances help fight cancer by focusing on specific targets that influence important signaling pathways in tumor cells[19]. Natural products like flavonoids, carotenoids, phenolic compounds, and terpenoids found in fruits, vegetables, spices, teas, and herbs are popular among cancer researchers because they are affordable, safe, and have low toxicity. Early-stage tumors can often be treated effectively with surgery and radiation, but for advanced or metastatic cancers, chemotherapy remains the main option. While common chemotherapy drugs can improve survival, they often come with serious side effects and long-term risks. Additionally, many cancers show resistance to standard chemotherapy treatments[20-23]. Despite this, chemotherapy is still the primary method for treating cancer, leading researchers to seek new compounds with fewer side effects. Natural products play a crucial role in this search.[24-25]. Enhancing the efficacy of conventional chemotherapy with natural, non-toxic substances is one potential strategy that may help lessen side effects and fight resistance. According to research, by targeting key signaling pathways, the combination of natural chemicals with traditional chemotherapy can lessen toxicity and fight drug resistance. The need for more research is highlighted by the potential of natural chemicals to improve chemotherapy results for cancer patients. To maximize their use, new natural substances must be found and their molecular mechanisms must be understood.[26].

➤ **Sesquiterpene lactones (STL):**

Throughout the plant kingdom, STLs are secondary metabolites derived from Asteraceae plants and belong to the subclass of sesquiterpenoids. Every part of the plant, including the roots, leaves, fruits, and flowers, produces these substances. They are structurally composed of 15 carbon atoms, mostly arranged in a cyclic pattern, and have an α -methylene- γ -lactone ring, which gives them a potent alkylation capacity.

[27,28]. According to recent studies, STLs can engage in a process called Michael-type addition with nucleophilic groups, such as those found in proteins with sulfhydryl groups. Numerous biological actions, such as anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, and noteworthy anticancer capabilities, have earned them recognition. Potential improvements in cancer treatment are indicated by the growing evidence of their anticancer benefits.[28,29].

➤ **Alantolactone (ALT)**

A vital component of many plants, alantolactone is particularly present in the root of *Inula helenium*, sometimes referred to as elecampane. This plant is indigenous to North America, Europe, and East Asia. Other species such as *Inula japonica*, *Aucklandia lappa*, *Inula racemosa*, *Inula royleana*, *Rudbeckia subtomentosa*, and *Radix inulae* can also provide ALT in addition to *Inula helenium*. For the purpose of separating natural chemicals, the extraction procedure is essential.[30-32,15]. ALT is extracted using a variety of processes, including conventional methods such solid-phase dispersion, heat reflux, and maceration, especially from *I. helenium*. To increase yield, more advanced extraction techniques have recently been developed. For example, Trendafilova and associates effectively extracted ALT in 2010 by employing ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) with 70% or 96% ethanol at room temperature for 30 minutes[33,34].

According to studies, this approach provides a higher yield of 18.65 mg/g and a faster extraction speed than conventional extraction methods. Zhao et al. extracted ALT in 2015 using microwave-assisted extraction with either 70% or 96% ethanol at 50 °C, yielding 31.83 mg/g, which is greater than that of UAE. According to research, this eudesmane-type STL has a number of biological actions, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties [35]. ALT is used in traditional medicine to treat conditions like TB, bronchitis, cancer, asthma, and chronic enterogastritis. [36,37]. Additionally, in vitro research indicates that this substance can stop the growth of many types of cancer cells, such as those from breast, colorectal, gastric, lung, and pancreatic tumors. via disrupting several signaling pathways, ALT may be able to stop cancer-related activities via influencing the cell cycle, cancer cell proliferation, invasion, metastasis, and apoptosis, according to mounting data. Given the importance of this mechanism in the development of cancer, the section that follows will examine in depth how ALT affects each of the mechanisms that have been covered. [38-40].

Fig.1 Structure of Alantolactone and Inula Helinum

➤ The Role or Mechanism of ALT in Human Cancers :

Lung Cancer:

Lactone, a substance often produced during metabolic processes, is the source of the metabolite alantolactone. Alantolactone and lung cancer, however, have not been found to be significantly associated by studies. Other related substances, including other lactones engaged in various metabolic pathways or in the context of cancer biology, might be on your mind. However, lactones and other metabolites can affect immunological response, inflammation, and cell signaling—all of which are important for the onset and spread of cancer, including lung cancer. [41,42]. It would be helpful to include more information if you are referring to a particular study or recent research, since the study of metabolic by-products in cancer is a developing subject with new discoveries being made on a regular basis. I would be happy to look into the connection between alantolactone and lung cancer further if you could provide a specific study or source.

I. Liver Cancer :The anticancer effects of alantolactone are facilitated through several significant mechanisms, which can be outlined as follows:

Induction of Apoptosis (Impaired Cell Death) Alantolactone primarily exhibits its anticancer effects by inducing malignant cells to undergo apoptosis. The term "apoptosis" describes the planned process of cell death that eliminates damaged or aberrant cells.[43].

(B). Mitochondrial Pathway of Apoptosis: Cytochrome c is released from the mitochondria into the cytosol as a result of alantolactone activating pathways that are reliant on the mitochondria. The caspases, a class of proteases necessary for the completion of apoptosis, are then activated by this release. In particular, it has been demonstrated that alantolactone promotes the production of pro-apoptotic proteins like Bax and decreases the levels of anti-apoptotic proteins like Bcl-2, which helps liver cancer cells die (Yuan et al., 2018). Alantolactone has been shown to facilitate the activation of caspase-3 and caspase-9, two essential elements of the apoptotic cascade. According to Li et al. (2020), this cascade is essential for the removal of cancer cells from liver tumors.

(C) Cell Cycle Arrest: In liver cancer cells, alantolactone has been shown to cause cell cycle arrest, especially at the G2/M checkpoint. This successfully stops tumor growth by stopping cancer cells from progressing through the cell cycle and dividing. **G2/M Phase Arrest:** By altering cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), which are crucial regulators of the G2/M transition, alantolactone disrupts the cell cycle. According to Zhang et al. (2019), this arrest aids in the inhibition of cancer cell proliferation.

(D) Regulation of Cyclin Proteins:It has been observed that cyclins such cyclin B1 and cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (CDK1), which are essential for the progression of the G2/M phase, are downregulated by alantolactone [44].

(E) Anti-Inflammatory Properties Chronic inflammation significantly contributes to the onset and advancement of liver cancer. Alantolactone exhibits anti-inflammatory characteristics that may help mitigate the inflammatory microenvironment linked to liver cancer, consequently hindering tumor development. **Suppression of NF- κ B Signaling:** Research indicates that alantolactone can inhibit the NF- κ B (nuclear factor-kappa B) signaling pathway, which plays a vital role in both inflammation and cancer progression. By reducing NF- κ B activity, alantolactone lowers the levels of inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β , all of which are implicated in the progression of liver cancer. **Decreased COX-2 Expression:** Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is an enzyme frequently overexpressed in various cancers, including liver cancer, and is responsible for producing pro-inflammatory prostaglandins. Alantolactone diminishes COX-2 expression, thereby lessening the inflammatory response that could otherwise promote tumor growth [45,46].

(F). Metastasis Inhibition One of the main causes of death for people with liver cancer is metastasis, the process by which the cancer spreads to other organs. It has been shown that alantolactone can prevent cancer cells from migrating and invading, two essential processes in metastasis. MMP Inhibition: Enzymes called matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) degrade the extracellular matrix, which facilitates the invasion and spread of tumor cells. Because alantolactone suppresses MMP production, cancer cells are prevented from spreading to other organs and attacking nearby tissues (Zhao et al., 2020) [47].

(G). Modulation of Essential Signaling Pathways

Alantolactone has an impact on a number of important signaling pathways that are necessary for liver cancer cells to survive, proliferate, and spread.

The PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway is essential for cell survival, proliferation, and metabolism and is commonly interfered with in liver cancer. Alantolactone has been shown to downregulate the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway, which reduces cell survival and promotes the growth of tumors.

MAPK/ERK Pathway: The survival, differentiation, and proliferation of cancer cells are all dependent on the MAPK/ERK signaling pathway. Alantolactone suppresses tumor development and promotes apoptosis by blocking ERK1/2 activation.[48].

(H). Synergistic Effects with Chemotherapy

Alantolactone has been studied for its potential to improve the effectiveness of standard chemotherapy. Its capacity to modulate key signaling pathways and trigger apoptosis may render it a valuable addition to combination therapies.

Chemosensitization: Certain studies have demonstrated that alantolactone can increase the sensitivity of liver cancer cells to chemotherapeutic agents such as cisplatin and doxorubicin. By inhibiting survival pathways in cancer cells, alantolactone may allow for lower doses of chemotherapeutic drugs, thereby reducing side effects (Zhang et al., 2019)[49].

(I). Hepatoprotective Properties

Notably, alantolactone also seems to possess hepatoprotective properties, which could be advantageous in liver cancer treatment, particularly when liver function is often impaired. Antioxidant Properties: Alantolactone has demonstrated antioxidant activity, which can safeguard liver cells from oxidative stress and damage. This is especially pertinent in liver cancer, where oxidative stress plays a role in both the initiation and progression of the disease

(III)Tumor :

Apoptosis Induced: It triggers apoptosis via a mitochondrial-dependent process that activates caspases and modifies the ratio of pro-apoptotic (Bax) to anti-apoptotic (Bcl-2) proteins, which helps tumor cells die.

Cell Cycle Arrest: It induces an arrest in the G2/M phase, hindering the division of tumor cells by influencing the activity of cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs).

Anti-Inflammatory Effects: Alantolactone acts to inhibit the NF- κ B signaling pathway and lowers COX-2 expression, which in turn diminishes inflammation that can promote tumor growth[51].

Inhibits Tumor Invasion: It decreases the expression of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and inhibits the process of epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), thereby restricting the spread of tumors.

Modulates Signaling Pathways: It disrupts essential signaling pathways such as PI3K/Akt/mTOR and MAPK/ERK, which slows tumor progression and improves the effectiveness of treatments.

Chemosensitization: It has the potential to amplify the effects of chemotherapy, which may allow for lower drug dosages and reduced side effects.

Neuroprotective: Alantolactone exhibits antioxidant properties, potentially safeguarding healthy brain tissue from damage during therapeutic interventions[52].

➤ **The effect of ALT on cancer cell apoptosis**

In healthy cells, apoptosis is a form of cell death that is designed to assist preserve a balance between cell survival and death. Many illnesses, including infections, heart disease, neurological disorders, and most notably, cancer, can result from this process not functioning correctly.

. In many cancer cells, this pathway is blocked, and using chemotherapy to trigger apoptosis is a key method in cancer treatment. Recent research has looked into how ALT can induce apoptosis, showing that it often leads to cell death in cancer cells. For example, treating MCF-7 cells with ALT caused them to change shape from diamond to round[53,54].

This substance increases the phosphorylation of p38 while also raising the levels of B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-2), Bcl-2-associated X protein, p53, caspase-3, and caspase-12. At the same time, it lowers nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) and p65 levels. Research indicates that this substance triggers apoptosis through the Nrf2, NF- κ B, and p38 MAPK pathways. By triggering the JNK and p38 MAPK signaling pathways, ALT successfully reduces medication resistance to oxaliplatin in colorectal cancer cells (HCT116 and RKO) and animal models, according to research by Peihai Cao and colleagues.

There have been conflicting recent results about autophagy's function in cancer cells. While some research suggests that autophagy causes type II programmed cell death, other studies show that it is active in particular cancer cells, preventing chemotherapy-induced apoptosis. Ruizhi and his team identified an alternate method for ALT's participation in apoptosis, finding that ALT reduces the expression and activity of CTSB/CTSD by lowering transcription factor EB (TFEB), which inhibits autophagic degradation. This has a major impact on the rise in drug resistance and cancer cell death. Additionally, HepG2 cells treated

with ALT undergo apoptosis, as demonstrated by increased levels of PARP and cleaved caspase-3, according to Xing and colleagues.[55-58].

ALT causes cells to produce more free radicals, which triggers apoptosis through the intrinsic route. Through this method, the Bax/Bcl-2 ratio is raised, cytoplasmic cytochrome c is released, caspases 9 and 3 are activated, and PARP is cleaved. According to research by Ding Y et al., applying ALT to colorectal cancer cells SW480 and SW1116 dramatically increases the generation of free radicals in these cells specifically. This leads to an increase in oxidized guanine (8-oxoG) and double-strand DNA breaks, which further promote apoptosis through the intrinsic pathway. Additionally, Yang et al. demonstrated how ALT causes osteosarcoma cells to undergo apoptosis by raising the levels of Bax, Bad, cleaved caspase-3, and cleaved PARP while lowering Bcl-2 levels.[59,60]. Furthermore, by suppressing cyclin B1 production, ALT stops the cell cycle at the G2/M phase. According to mechanistic studies, ALT produces these effects by preventing serine 9 phosphorylation in GSK3 β , which leads to the β -catenin protein being degraded and the Wnt/ β -Catenin signaling pathway being suppressed. Additionally, ALT inhibits signaling pathways linked to human metastasis, such as p38, ERK1/2, and JNK MAPK.[61,62].

In a different study, Maryam et al. found that when ALT is applied to A549 lung cancer cells, endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress and mitochondrial malfunction cause cell death. Subsequent research revealed that ALT causes A549 cells to undergo apoptosis by increasing the levels of cleaved PARP, Bax, and Bad while lowering Bcl-2 and triggering caspases 3 and 9. The findings further indicated that ALT might trigger ER-stress-induced apoptosis via raising eIF2 α phosphorylation and ATF4 and CHOP levels.[63]. Liu and colleagues demonstrated that ALT similarly induced apoptosis in two other lung cancer cell lines, NCI-H1299 and Anip973, by impacting the bcl-2 family. Their findings highlighted two critical events: the increased phosphorylation and activation of p38, which subsequently activates the p38 signaling pathway. Moreover, ALT was shown to inhibit the translocation of NF- κ B from the cytosol to the nucleus and to diminish the expression of genes associated with this transcription factor in leukemia stem cells derived from AML patients, without adversely affecting normal blood cells. In animal studies, ALT exhibited no side effects or toxicity in normal Kunming mice, while significantly reducing tumor size. The investigation into the underlying molecular mechanisms revealed that ALT enhances its apoptotic and anti-tumor effects by obstructing the NF- κ B signaling pathway and modulating the genes regulated by this transcription factor[64,65]. In another investigation, Ding and colleagues discovered that ALT had little effect on healthy blood cells but selectively caused cell death in leukemia stem cells (LSCs) from individuals with myeloid leukemia (AML). Tests on live Kunming mice demonstrated that ALT significantly decreased tumor size while having no negative side effects. Subsequent investigation revealed that ALT's ability to reduce tumors and cause cell death is linked to its suppression of the NF- κ B signaling system and its effects on the genes that are regulated by this pathway.[66-71].

Fig. 2 Signaling pathways overview targeted by ALT.

Alantolactone fights cancer by targeting many signaling pathways. By inhibiting the enzymes glutathione reductase (GR) and thioredoxin reductase (TrxR), it raises reactive oxygen species (ROS), which triggers the mitochondrial pathway and results in cell death. By blocking GR, ALT also lowers glutathione (GSH) levels and has an impact on STAT3, a protein connected to the proliferation and metastasis of cancer cells.

[72,73]. Additionally, ROS can trigger apoptosis through pathways like p38 MAPK. ALT also causes endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress via eIF2 α , leading to cell death. Another way ALT promotes apoptosis is by blocking autophagy, inhibiting the transcription factor EB (TFEB) and activating the protein complex AP2M1. Furthermore, ALT increases the presence of Nrf2 in the nucleus, contributing to its anti-cancer effects by also inhibiting the NF- κ B and PI3K-Akt pathways.[74-75]. Shi et al. presented a novel approach to understanding the mechanisms by which ALT combats tumors. Their research demonstrated that in Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL), ALT operates effectively in both living organisms and laboratory environments by inhibiting autophagy and inducing cell death. Further investigations indicated that ALT decreases the LC3-II / LC3-I ratio and Beclin1 levels while increasing p62 levels through the upregulation of the protein complex AP2M1. Moreover, the application of rapamycin, which promotes autophagy, diminishes ALT's capacity to induce cell death, thereby underscoring the relationship between autophagy and cell death. While ALT exhibits anti-tumor properties across various cancers, studies suggest it does not adversely affect normal cells or produce side effects in laboratory settings. Given that ALT selectively targets cancer cells without harming healthy ones, additional research is necessary to thoroughly investigate its potential as a cancer treatment.[76-78].

➤ **ALT and oxidative stress:**

A group of reactive chemicals known as reactive oxygen species (ROS) are essential for controlling a number of signaling pathways. Elevated metabolic rates in cancer cells lead to more hypoxia and the generation of free radicals. Cancer cells strengthen their enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant defenses to fight these free radicals.

[79]. Interestingly, the increased generation of free radicals may be useful in destroying tumor cells. A basic mechanism used in radiation therapy, some chemotherapy drugs, and natural treatment modalities, programmed cell death can be triggered by this rise in free radicals within cancer cells. By blocking glutathione reductase (GR), thioredoxin reductase (TrxR), and catalase, ALT raises free radical levels in B cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia (B-ALL), causing DNA damage and eventual cell death, according to research by Xiaoguang et al. Similarly, it has been demonstrated that ALT increases the generation of free radicals, which causes gastric cancer cells (BGC-823) to undergo apoptosis.[80]. By elevating oxidative stress and decreasing glutathione (GSH) levels, Khan et al. investigated the effect of ALT on Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) and discovered that it induces apoptosis in U87 cells. According to other research, ALT promotes apoptosis by raising the levels of p53, Bax, PARP, caspase 3, and caspase 9 while lowering Bcl-2. [81].

➤ **ALT and cell cycle**

The cell cycle is a well controlled mechanism that promotes genetic material replication and subsequent cell division. Numerous proteins and signaling pathways regulate this regulation, protecting the genome and identifying DNA damage to stop genetic defects from being passed on to daughter cells.[82-83]. Cancer cells often show defects in cell cycle checkpoints, which leads to unchecked cell division and disruptions in the regulation of the cell cycle. As a result, controlling the cell cycle has emerged as a key goal for cancer treatments. According to recent studies, some substances, most notably ALT, can affect the cell cycle by having inhibitory effects.[84-85]. For example, Peng et al. showed that treatment of SK-MES-1 cells from lung squamous carcinoma results in a G1/G0 phase cell cycle termination and a reduction in CDK4, CDK6, cyclin D3, and cyclin D1 levels. Additionally, Yibing et al. discovered that by blocking the Nf-κB signaling pathway, treating HELA cells stops the cell cycle in the G2/M phase.[86].

➤ **ALT and metastasis**

Despite a great deal of research over the years, metastasis remains a major cause of cancer-related mortality. [87]. Instead of the main tumors itself, the majority of cancer-related deaths are caused by the spread of cancer cells to distant organs. Determining possible therapy targets requires an understanding of the cellular and molecular mechanisms underlying metastasis. Numerous signaling pathways are linked to the metastasis of cancer cells and could be targets for intervention, including GF/RAS/RAF/MEK/ER, PI3K/Akt/mTOR, HGF/Met, Wnt/β-catenin, VEGF, Notch, Hedgehog, STAT3, and NF-κB.[88]. Among these, the STAT3 pathway is particularly significant in the advancement of cancer, frequently activated by cytokines, growth factors, and oncogenic proteins, and plays a pivotal role in the metastatic process.[89]. Consequently, inhibiting the STAT3 pathway presents a promising approach to curtailing metastasis. Research indicates

that ALT can effectively block the phosphorylation of STAT3.[90].NF- κ B, another transcription factor impacted by ALT, is often overexpressed in a variety of cancers. There is evidence linking increased NF- κ B levels to important functions like inflammation, cell survival, proliferation, and—most importantly—cancer cell metastasis. He et al.'s study showed that ALT therapy decreased NF- κ B activation in the gastric cancer cell lines BGC-823 and SGC-7901.[91].Additionally, their results showed that ALT greatly reduced the levels of the metalloproteinases MMP-2, MMP-7, and MMP-9 in these cells, reducing colony formation, migration, and invasion. Similarly, ALT suppressed NF- κ B activation in glioblastoma cells, according to Xun et al. Furthermore, according to molecular modeling, ALT blocks IKK β 's ATP binding site, which raises MMP-2 and MMP-9 production and may promote metastasis. Similar outcomes were reported by Liu et al. in lung cancer cells.[92].

➤ **ALT and TGF- β signaling pathway**

Numerous biological functions, including migration, apoptosis, differentiation, cell proliferation, and tumor development, depend on the TGF- β signaling system. When the TGF- β ligand is activated, TGF β receptor type I (RI) becomes engaged and then binds to TGF β receptor type II (RII) [93].This binding event causes Smad2/3, also known as R-Smads, to become phosphorylated. Smad2/3 joins forces with Smad4 after phosphorylation and moves into the nucleus, where it controls target gene expression [94].Studies on several types of cancer cells have shown that these cells have a substantial overexpression of Smad3. Additionally, studies indicate a favorable relationship between Smad3 expression levels and cancer cell metastasis. [95].According to a recent study by Ying et al., ALT affects the TGF- β signaling pathway. At 5- μ g/ml, they found that ALT activates the activin/SMAD3 pathway in human colon cancer HCT-8 cells without negatively impacting normal human cells. By interfering with the Cripto-1 and activin complex, this activation particularly prevents the development of cancer cells. By blocking the TGF β 1 signaling pathway, different ALT and isolantolactone compounds can lessen lung fibrosis, according to another study by Li et al. These compounds increase the production of α -SMA by blocking the phosphorylation of Smad3 in the presence of TGF β -1 [96,97]. ALT has the ability to alter the TGF β pathway, but more investigation is required to fully understand its molecular processes.[98].

➤ **ALT as STAT3 selective inhibitor**

Numerous biological functions, including migration, apoptosis, differentiation, cell proliferation, and tumor development, depend on the TGF- β signaling system. When the TGF- β ligand is activated, TGF β receptor type I (RI) becomes engaged and then binds to TGF β receptor type II (RII) [99].This binding event causes Smad2/3, also known as R-Smads, to become phosphorylated. Smad2/3 joins forces with Smad4 after phosphorylation and moves into the nucleus, where it controls target gene expression.[100]Studies on a variety of cancer cell types have shown that these cells exhibit a substantial overexpression sSmad3.[101].Additionally, studies indicate a favorable relationship between Smad3 expression levels and cancer cell metastasis. ALT affects the TGF- β signaling pathway.[102]. At 5- μ g/ml, they found that ALT activates the activin/SMAD3 pathway in human colon cancer HCT-8 cells without negatively impacting

normal human cells. By interfering with the Cripto-1 and activin complex, this activation particularly prevents the development of cancer cells. By blocking the TGF β 1 signaling pathway, different ALT and isolantolactone compounds can lessen lung fibrosis, These compounds increase the production of α -SMA by blocking the phosphorylation of Smad3 in the presence of TGF β -1. Although ALT shows promise in modifying the TGF β pathway, more investigation is required to fully understand its molecular underpinnings.[103].

➤ Conclusion:

Cancer is a significant problem for communities worldwide. Even with ongoing research to find effective treatments, it continues to challenge the medical community. Natural products have been used for treating various illnesses, particularly cancer, for many years, making this a crucial area for discovering new drugs. STLs represent a well-known group of natural products that have shown various biological activities, including anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects. ALT, part of the STLs family, has caught the interest of cancer researchers because of its diverse biological functions. Research indicates that ALT can promote cell death and hinder the cell cycle and metastasis by acting on different signaling pathways such as P38, STAT3, NF-kB, and AKT. Current findings suggest that ALT's anticancer properties arise from increasing free radicals and inhibiting antioxidant enzymes. Although several studies have explored ALT, most have concentrated on cellular models, with limited research on its effects in animal models. More comprehensive molecular studies are needed to clarify how ALT interacts with cancer cells and to assess its therapeutic potential. Furthermore, there is a lack of research on ALT's structure, highlighting the need for detailed studies on modifying and developing anticancer agents based on ALT.

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